

O20. Optimizing CO₂ capture in the transformation of phosphogypsum to new raw materials with caustic solution

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The phosphogypsum (PG) valorization is the main goal of EU Horizon Europe project FIC-FIGHTERS [1]. In this project, the University of Sevilla, in collaboration with CapturaCO₂, S.L, (the patent owner), is employing the sodium hydroxide chemical route [2] to transform phosphogypsum into new raw materials, such sodium sulphate or calcite.

To optimize this process, we have monitored the electrical conductivity of the reaction as the key parameter for assessing the optimal reaction time. To have a reference for the following experiments with PG, the experiments have been carried out with gypsum and caustic soda of reaction grade purity, varying the concentration of NaOH, the amount of gypsum (or PG), and the reaction time to produce calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) or Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) under the best possible conditions with minimal water consumption.

Figure 1. Left) Electrical conductivity depends on the reaction time. Right) SEM image from a Ca(OH)₂ obtained during one of the experiments.

Keywords: Phosphogypsum; CO₂ Capture; PCC; Valorization.

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